

FEATURES OF THE INITIAL STAGE OF COMPETITIVE ACTIVITY OF YOUTH 13-15 YEARS OLD IN SPORTS HAND FIGHT FIGHTS

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Annotation. *The image is considered as a stereotyped image of a particular object that exists in the mass consciousness. The development of a model for the formation of the image of a future specialist in the context of health is possible in the context of the implementation of personality-oriented pedagogy, in which the understanding of the educational impact is defined as the development of individuality in a person.*

The purpose of creating a model for forming the image of a future specialist in the context of health in higher education is to expand and deepen the possibility of self-realization of future specialists at the level of professionally significant, personally and socially desirable standards.

There are three stages that a future specialist goes through in the process of creating an image in the context of health, as well as goals, content, methods and forms, means and methods, conditions and criteria for evaluating this process.

The sport of hand-to-hand combat is a complex martial art and consists of three main areas: sports hand-to-hand combat - covering pre-conscription youth [2,4,9], police and army hand-to-hand combat - performing the tasks of applied training of law enforcement officers and military personnel [3].

Sports hand-to-hand combat, approved in 2003 by RosSport, is being developed within the framework of the All Uzbek Federation of Sports Hand-to-

Hand Combat. The main tasks of the Federation's activities are the development of mass sports and sports of higher achievements [4].

Sports hand-to-hand combat competitions consist of two sections - competitions for the demonstration of software technical complexes - KATA, and competitions for duels - KUMITE [2].

The age of 13-15 years is the initial stage of competitive activity according to the rules of sports hand-to-hand combat [4].

One of the most important problems of elite sport, and martial arts in particular, is the problem of many years of technical and tactical training.

According to many authors [2,5,6] of various types of martial arts, the initial stage of competitive activity is characterized by technical and tactical monotony, coaching athletes for results due to the functional reserves of the body, instead of searching and implementing new methods of technical and tactical training.

According to the authors [5,6], there is a regularity in the narrowing of the technical arsenal with the growth of sportsmanship, the emergence of crown techniques adapted to the individual characteristics of the athlete.

According to the data of pedagogical observations of competitive activity of athletes, there is a monotony and low variability of technical and tactical actions, even at the initial stage of performances, while it is from adolescence that technical and tactical training should include the entire technical and tactical arsenal, in conditions of its natural narrowing and individualization at the stages of sports improvement and higher sportsmanship [6].

According to pedagogical observations, the effectiveness of the duel directly depends on the variability of the technique and tactics of the athlete, which increases with the growth of his technical and tactical skills.

In the theory of sports, the opinion has long been expressed that in complex coordination , situational and psycho-stress sports, technical and tactical training

is in the first place. In this aspect, there is still unused, significant potential for improving the quality of training of athletes by improving the content, sequence and methodology of tactical and technical training [6].

Sports hand-to-hand combat is a complex martial art that combines striking techniques with hands and feet, as well as wrestling techniques in a standing and lying position. Thus, sports hand-to-hand combat is a technically complex sport, and the more complex the technique, the higher the judges' score [8].

The nature of the duel, as a rule, is combinational, i.e. the athlete who owns a wide arsenal of techniques and tactics wins. This is primarily due to the lack of victory by knockout and a wide range of possible options for using the technique, in contrast to boxing, kickboxing, types of wrestling, army and police hand-to-hand combat, where, along with a playful, combinational manner, there are tempo and power manners of conducting a duel [2, 5,8].

According to many authors [1,5,6,8], the stage of initial training in all sports, including martial arts, is the most important and fundamental. The whole future path and the expected success in big-time sports depend on how competently and rationally the training process of young athletes is planned and carried out.

Many authors [5,6] believe that it is the tactical preparedness of an athlete that has a decisive influence on his success - it gives stable positive results of performance in competitions.

Questions of tactical training must be approached from an early age, since the lack of tactics is especially visible at adolescence, where there is a lot of action and little sense. Only over the years, through trial and error, an athlete acquires a reserve of tactical skill [5,6].

In sports hand-to-hand combat, we have not been able to find any works devoted to tactics at the present time. We turned to the issues of combat sports tactics [3,5,7,8].

The main content of the competitive activity of an athlete in a duel is the performance of elementary, basic technical and tactical actions in order to obtain an assessment in accordance with the rules of the competition. The main focus of activity in a duel is the performance of technical actions (techniques and defenses). Auxiliary - the performance of tactical actions that create a certain situation that ensures the implementation of the main technical actions.

Consider the tactical and technical content of sports hand-to-hand combat. As a result of the analysis of the literature on tactics in martial arts, it was revealed that the motor component of the action is excluded from the definition of tactics. Tactics is only about deciding what to do and when, and technology helps to implement these decisions.

The tactics of a sports duel is the intellectual activity of an athlete in a duel, aimed at setting goals and making decisions about the use of a particular technique at a certain point in time to achieve victory over the opponent.

What are these solutions that are implemented through technical skill?

Directly in a duel, these are mainly decisions on attack, defense and counterattack, we are not talking now about preparatory tactical tasks - reconnaissance, camouflage, challenge, interference, which are implemented both in the preparation of the main tactical task and during its implementation.

to build tactics only on the basis of the available stock of technical skills.

According to the rules of competitions in sports hand-to-hand combat, technical actions are evaluated in the following sections of technology: punches, kicks , throws, painful holds, suffocating holds, and they are evaluated differently , i.e., as already mentioned, than The more difficult the technique and technical combinations, the higher the score.

The tactics and technique of martial arts are organically combined in the form of technical and tactical actions [8]. Consider them in relation to sports hand-to-hand combat.

In sports hand-to-hand combat, where a different technical arsenal of martial arts is used, the implementation of an attack or counterattack can be a punch or a kick, a throw, a painful or asphyxiating technique, depending on the prepared or favorable situation. Therefore, an attack or counterattack can be simple - without preparation or complex - with preparation.

Any technical-tactical combination includes preparatory actions that create a favorable situation, and basic technical actions that complete the combination and bring an assessment or result.

Attack and counterattack consists of technical actions, called basic technical actions, because. they bring results.

Preparation also consists of technical actions, called auxiliary - because. do not bring results on their own, but only in combination with the main technical actions. These are stances, movements, grips, ways to unbalance, protection, deliberate waiting. Training, along with auxiliary technical actions, can also be in the form of false attacks-calls, combinations of basic technical actions - technical combinations, as a result of which a conceived technique is hidden under distracting false actions.

Attack without preparation - a single technical action can be implemented at a favorable moment: when the opponents are mutually approaching at the distance necessary for the attack, as an attack at a favorable moment by approach; when the enemy retreats to the attack distance, as an attack at an opportune moment by pursuit.

Complex attack - includes preparation that interferes with the opponent before performing the main technical action: a false attack (feint) in combination with the main technical action; unbalancing in combination with the main technical action. As well as an attack at an opportune moment, it can be executed by approaching and chasing.

Preliminary preparation, distracting the enemy from adequate defense,

brings more results than a simple attack. The counterattack includes protection from an enemy attack with the transition to active attacking actions.

A counterattack without preparation can be carried out: in anticipation of the attacking action of the enemy that has begun, i.e. oncoming counterattack, when approaching the enemy or leaving the line of attack, the defense in this case is movement; as a response after defending against an enemy attack, i.e. retaliatory counterattack, after approaching or leaving the line of attack with a transition to active attacking actions.

A complex counterattack - with preliminary preparation by a call, as well as a counterattack without preparation, is implemented as a counterattack and as a response.

The call to attack the enemy is carried out, as a rule, by a false attack (feint), or positional neglect of defense (trap). Knowledge of the tactical and technical structures of actions makes it possible to move on to the purposeful formation of skills in athletes to control the actions of the enemy in conflict interaction with him [7].

On the basis of the identified tactical manners of the implementation of technology, we have developed protocols for the registration of technical and tactical actions.

Video filming and analysis of the competitive activity of athletes aged 13-15 were carried out. The object of the analysis was all fights of young men aged 13-15 at the championship of Uzbekistan in sports hand-to-hand combat in Mendeleevsk on 21-23.04.2006. As a result of the analysis, the technical and tactical content of the competitive activity of young men of this age was revealed.

A total of 122 fights were registered and analyzed. Each effective technical action was recorded without taking into account the quantitative assessment for its implementation. All technical and technical-tactical actions recorded in the conditions of the competition were taken as 100%.

Table 1 presents the technical and tactical content of the fights of young men aged 13-15 in the championship of Uzbekistan in sports hand-to-hand combat. The table shows that the most frequently implemented tactical manner is an attack without preparation with mutual approach - at a favorable moment - 40.7%.

In a counterattacking manner, a counterattack without preparation is most often used - ahead of the curve - 30.6%. The most unrealizable tactical manners are counterattacks with preparation by calling a false attack. The counterattack with preparation was 0.5%, the response was 0.77%. This indicates the shortcomings of the tactical training of young athletes. In terms of the percentage of effective technique, punching technique with hands is in the first place - 77.93%, then punching technique with legs is - 16.02%, a very small percentage of throws - 5.94% , effective ground technique and technique in the prone wrestling are completely absent, which indicates insufficient preparedness in the sections of throws, painful holds and suffocations.

The most effective is the striking technique with hands and feet, because. strikes, being independent technical actions, are also included in complex technical and tactical actions. For example, a strike after being unbalanced or thrown.

Table 1

Technical and tactical content of the fights of young men aged 13-15 in the championship of Uzbekistan in sports hand-to-hand combat (in%)

TACTICAL MANNER PERFORMANCE OF THE RESULT TECHNICAL		SECTIONS TECHNIQUE AND X					Itoro:	
		Udayr ukami	Udayn ogami	Broski	Bole-in th	suffocati on		
A T A K	PROSTAY (bez pabout dot about ki) _	Prioboudnom close proximity _	28, 75	10, 1	1, 81	0	0	40, 7
		PriPsecution _	4, 66	2, 84	0	0	0	7, 5

A	COMPOUND ----- (with preparation)	In com bina tio n _ ----- a	5 , 44	2 , 07	0.77 __	0	0	8 , 28
		Pos ert ion _ from r a v n o v e s i a	3.1	0	0	0	0	3 , 1
T O O N T	PRO S T A Y (b e z p a b o u t d o t a b o u t k i) _ _	Th e r e _ _ _ c o n t r a t a k a -	28 , 75	0.25 _ _	1.55 _ _	0	0	30 , 6
		Re p l y _ _ _ _ c o n t r a t a k a - p o s l e f o r s h i e l d s	6 , 21	0.51 _ _	1 , 81	0	0	8 , 53
R A T A K A	COMPOUND ----- (with preparation _ ----- - y z o v o m) _	Co u n t e r a t t a c k _ _ -----	0.25 _ _	0.25 _ _	0	0	0	0.5 _ _
		Re t a l i a t o r y c o u n t e r a t t a c k _ _ -----	0.77 _ _	0	0	0	0	0.77 _ _
I t o r o :			77 , 93	16 , 02	5 , 94	0	0	100

Table 2 shows the list and percentage of striking techniques with arms and legs. The table shows that there are more punches (33.65%) than effective actions (25.18%). There is a uniformity of technique, namely direct punches - the highest value - 22.1% of 25.18% of the effective technique of punches hands. There are no blows from the side and from below, almost no elbow strikes, - implemented within the framework of the rules for sports hand-to-hand combat only in the torso, t.to. on at high speeds, they are difficult to control and, if hit to the head, lead to injuries.

With kicks, we also see that there are much more attempts (32.24%), how effective actions (5.17%). There is a uniformity of technique, namely circular kick

from the outside - the highest value - 4.77% of 5.17% of the effective technique kicks. In the percussion technique of the legs, there are attempts to perform complex coordination of strikes. However, knee strikes are almost never realized 0.08% of 5.17%.

Along with the uniformity of technical actions, there is a small variability efficient technology.

The variability of technique was defined as the ratio of the sum of non-repeating options for effective technical actions to the sum of their possible options multiplied by one hundred percent. The variability of technology should strive for one hundred percent.

It was revealed that the variability of punches is 40%. Stroke variability legs is also 40%.

table 2

The list and percentage ratio of punching technique with hands and feet in the fights of boys aged 13-15 in the championship of Uzbekistan in sports hand-to-hand combat

U d a r n a i t e x n i c k			Efficient technology __	U n e s u l t a t _ ___ (p a r i r o v a n a i) t e x n i c k	T e x n i c k a w i t h v i o l a t i n g _ _ _ _ _ p r a i l
R u k a m i	K u l a k o m	straight ___	22 , 1 %	29 , 8	1 , 5
		R o u g r o u n d i n t	1 , 25 %	1 , 6	0,4 _
		R o o n o o o o n _ _	1.75 _ _ %	2 , 17	0.58 _
		From b o k u	0	0 %	0
	With	0	0 %	0	
	L o c t e m	With	0	0 %	0
		From b o k u	0	0 %	0
		From the top	0 , 08 %	0 , 08	0
		I N f r o m t o r o u	0	0 %	0
		Back _	0	0 %	0
I t o r o r y t o a m a n d :			25 , 18 %	33 , 65 %	2 , 48
N o g	S t o p o y	Direct _ _ _ _ _	0	1 , 25	0 , 16
		R o o n o o o o n	4 , 77 %	29	0.67 _

ami		R o u g r o u n d i	0	0.92 _	0
		IN from t o r	0 , 16 %	0.58 _	0
		Direct _ _ _ _ _	0 , 16 %	0.25 _	0
	C o l e n	Direct _ _ _ _ _	0	0 , 08	0
		With	0 , 08 %	0 , 16	0
		From b o k u	0	0 %	0
		From the	0	0 %	0
		From the	0	0 %	0
I t o r o n o g a m a n d :		5 , 17 %	32 , 24 %	0.83 _	
I t o r o r u k a m i A n d n o g		30 , 35 %	65 , 89 %	3 , 31	
I t o r o :		100			

Further in table 3 we see a list of throws adapted to sports hand-to-hand combat, and the percentage of effective throws in the fights of young men 13-15 years old.

The variability of shots was determined by the ratio of 8 variants of the effective executions to 20 possible, adapted to the rules of sports hand-to-hand combat, variants of throws and amounted to 40%. There is a uniformity of throwing technique. Front leg grab throws are – 34%; Throws with the back trip from the grip of the leg 26% of the effective technique of throws.

I.A. Bushin points out the negative role of leg grab throws under conditions complex martial arts, tk. this leads to the capture of the neck under the shoulder, counter blows knees and therefore injury to the attacker. Leg grab throws are recommended perform when capturing the attacking leg of the enemy [2].

Three lever attempts were recorded in the ground and prone wrestling techniques elbow across across the pelvis and one attempt at an elbow knot across. Effective painful no admissions were found. Strangulation attempts with the forearm by capturing the neck under the shoulder on horseback in front - four, attempts to strangle with kimono lapels in front - three. There were no effective

strangulations.

Table 3

The list of throws adapted to sports hand-to-hand combat, and the percentage of effective throws in the fights of boys aged 13-15

Throw class according to Yu.A. Shulike [9]	Throw term according to E.M. Chumakov [24]	%
leaning over	Legs (legs) in front	34%
	Toe-down from the inside	0%
	Snatch (snip from the inside from the grip of the leg)	0%
	Rear footrest (from foot grip)	26%
	Lateral undercut (from the grip of the leg)	4.3%
turning away	Through the thigh (through the back)	4.3%
	Kicking the front footrest off your knee	0%
	front footrest	0%
	Pickup from the inside	4.3%
	Under both legs	0%
sagging	Front undercut	4.3%
	Through the chest	0%
	Side kick heel slip	0%
	Foot lift (shin)	0%
	Coups after takeoff (kip)	13 %
tipping over	Through the chest with a girth at the back	8.7%
	Reverse leg pull	0%
	Rear heel kick	0%
	Foot toe	0%
	Scissors	0%

Total:	100%
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Table 4 shows the results of mathematical processing of the obtained indicators of competitive activity of boys aged 13-15 in the championship of Uzbekistan in sports hand-to-hand combat.

The performance in the sections of technology was determined as the ratio of the number effective technique to the total amount of technical actions in this section multiplied one hundred percent. The effectiveness of sections of technology should strive for one hundred percent. The effectiveness of punches is 40%, the effectiveness of kicks is 14%, shot efficiency - 28%. The effectiveness of parterre techniques and techniques prone wrestling is 0%.

The effectiveness of the fight was determined as the ratio of the number of effective technique to the total amount of technical actions of this fight multiplied by one hundred percent. The effectiveness of the duel should strive for one hundred percent. Efficiency bout as a whole was 30%. The effectiveness of fighting in the stance was determined by the ratio of the sum of effective techniques of punches, kicks and throws to the sum of all technical actions and amounted to 30%.

The effectiveness of the prone wrestling is 0%.

As we can see from Table 4, the average number of technical actions in one match is 11.47. The duel among young men aged 13-15 lasts two minutes. Therefore, on average, every 10.46 seconds, athletes perform technical actions: either attacking, or defending from an enemy attack, or counterattacking, - the intensity of the fight is high and the athletes must be functionally ready conduct from two to ten fights in one day.

Table 4

Summary table of the results of mathematical processing of the obtained indicators of competitive activity of boys aged 13-15 in the championship of

Uzbekistan in sports hand-to-hand combat

In all of the fights _ _ _ _ _	112
All in all _ _ _ _ _ d i s t v y _	1285
A verage number of technical _ _ _ _ _ d i	11 , 47
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ at d a r o v r u k ami	40 %
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ at d a r o v n o g ami	14 %
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ b r o s k o v	28 %
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ suffocation _ _ _ _ _	0 %
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ b o l e s _ _ p r e m s _	0 %
Variability _ _ _ _ _ at d a r o v r u k ami	40 %
Variability _ _ _ _ _ at d a r o v n o g ami	40 %
Variability _ _ _ _ _ b r o s k o v	40 %
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ b o i V with t o y k e _	thirty%
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ b o r b s _ l y i n g _ _	0 %
Efficiency _ _ _ _ _ p o e d i n c a V c e l o m	thirty %

The quality of execution of equipment acquires a special role, because. technique is execution actions with the greatest efficiency at the lowest energy costs . But we have reverse picture. A lot of ineffective technique, as a result of irrational execution of technical actions. And the ability to apply a technical action refers to tactical training means that it is the latter that suffers.

Conclusions:

- It was revealed that in sports hand-to-hand combat at the initial stage of the competitive activity of boys aged 13-15 there is monotony and low variability technical and tactical actions;
- Competitive activity of young men aged 13-15 in sports hand-to-hand combat ineffective and is 30%. The reason is the large number ineffective technique;

- There is significant potential to increase the effectiveness of technical actions by improving the content and methodology of tactical and technical preparation;
- The revealed tactical manners of performing effective techniques can be used in the technique of technical and tactical training at the initial stage learning;
- It is necessary to comprehensively prepare children for competitive activities in sports hand-to-hand combat - from 10-12 years old - from the stage of initial training. special give place in training to technical and tactical training. Teach broad an arsenal of technical actions available to children aged 10-12, with the passage tactical manners of implementation of technology.

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